

**HYDROXYUREA-INDUCED HAND FOOT SYNDROME IN A PATIENT WITH
THROMBOCYTOSIS-HIGH RISK: A CASE REPORT**

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ABSTRACT

Hand-foot syndrome (HFS) is a well-known adverse event associated with long-term use of hydroxyurea. It starts from weeks to months after initiation of hydroxyurea. Hydroxyurea is used to manage myeloproliferative disorders like polycythemia vera, essential thrombocythemia, psoriasis, acute myeloid leukemia, meningioma, melanoma, and ovarian cancer. **Presentation:** This case report highlights the hydroxyurea causing hand-foot syndrome in a patient with JAK2 V617-positive essential thrombocythemia. **Conclusion:** This case report emphasized the need of early recognition of the hand foot syndrome in patient with JAK2 V617-positive essential thrombocythemia, and timely intervention of the prolonged using of hydroxyurea causing hand-foot syndrome. Multidisciplinary intervention, including counseling by a clinical pharmacist will ensure the benefit to the patient

KEYWORDS: Hand-foot syndrome (HFS), JAK2 V617- positive, thrombocythemia, intervention.

INTRODUCTION

Hand-foot syndrome (HFS), also known as “acral erythema” or “palmar-plantar erythrodysesthesia” or “toxic erythema of palms and soles” or “Burgdorf syndrome,” is a known and relatively rare side effect of the chemotherapy drug hydroxyurea.^[1] The pathogenesis of hand-foot syndrome (HFS) is not known. It is believed to be a toxic reaction due to the local accumulation of the drug.^[2] Hydroxyurea is particularly a drug of choice as a first-line treatment for intermediate- to high-risk essential thrombocythemia.^[3] The reaction is variably reversible with discontinuation of the medication but symptoms of pain and discomfort can persist for months.^[4] In a large retrospective review of patients with myeloproliferative neoplasms treated with hydroxyurea, fewer than 10% of patients treated with hydroxyurea developed any mucocutaneous toxicities, with more than 80% comprising cutaneous ulceration and oral toxicity.^[5]

CASE PRESENTATION

A 70-year-old female patient presented with complaints of black-colored palms and soles and nails since 1 month and burning sensation over the abdomen since 10 days

during the course of hydroxyurea which she was taking since 2 month. She has no pain on her palms and sole, and she reported that the complaints are worsening on taking hydroxyurea. she was the conformed case of thrombocytosis-high risk JAK2 V617 positive.

Past Medical History

HTN since 5 years on medication, Liver abscess, L4-L5 spondylolisthesis, and perivascular disease (PVD) in the right toe.

Treatment History

Tab Telma 40mg.

Allergies

No known drug and food allergies.

Family History

History of mother having cancer

Personal History

- Sleep And Appetite-Normal
- Bowel And Bladder Habits-Normal

➤ Mixed Normal Diet.

Obstetric History

P4L4 menopause

General Examination

- The patient was conscious, oriented, and cooperative. □
- Well-nourished, moderately built. □
- No pallor, icterus, cyanosis, clubbing, pedal edema, or lymphadenopathy. □
- No signs of dehydration or cachexia.

Systemic examination

● Cardiovascular system

- Heart sounds are heard clearly and are normal with no murmurs.
- The pulse in both wrists (radial arteries) is felt at the same time indicate normal blood flow to both arms.

- The wrist pulse and groin pulse (femoral artery) occurs at the same time indicates normal blood flow from heart to the lower body.

● Respiratory system

Normal bilateral Air Entry with Normal vesicular breath sounds.

● Central nervous system

- Glasgow comma scale : 15/15- the patient is fully conscious and alert and
- The neurological findings are normal with no focal neurological deficits.

● Abdominal examination

Soft, non-tender and bowel sounds are present.

Laboratory investigations

Table 1: MPN(myeloproliferative neoplasam) reflex panel test.

MPN REFLEX PANEL TEST	
JAK2 V617F	DETECTED
BCR-ABL1 Major transcript P210	NOT DETECTED
BCR-ABL1 Minor transcript P190	NOT DETECTED
MPL W515L MUTATION	NOT DETECTED
MPL W515K MUTATION	NOT DETECTED
MPL W515A MUTATION	NOT DETECTED
MPL 5505N MUTATION	NOT DETECTED
Calreticulin Type 1 Mutation	NOT DETECTED
Calreticulin Type 2 Mutation	NOT DETECTED

The findings of MPN reflex panel test JAK2 V617F (janus kinase 2 valine -to-phenylalanine) positive indicates a myeloproliferative disorder.

Table 2: Hemoglobin, total leucocytes count, neutrophylis, lymphocytes, platelets, TSH, Vit b12, Vit D, uric acid, creatinine.

PARAMETERS	RESULT	REFERANCE VALUES	INTERPRETATION
Hemoglobin	11.8	12.0-15.0 g/dl	Borderline low
TOTAL LEUCOCYTES COUNT	7250	4.0-10.0 x 10 ⁹ /L	With in normal range
NEUTROPHILS	68	40-80%	With in normal range
LYMPHOCYTES	26%	20-40%	With in normal range
PLATELETS	1425	150 - 400 10 ³ /μL	Severely elevated
OTHER REVELENT TEST		-	
TSH	6.92	0.35-4.94 mIU/L	Elevated
VIT B12	281	200-900 pg/mL	Borderline low
VIT D	45.17	30-100 ng/mL	With in normal range
URIC ACID	5.8	2.7-7.3 mg/dL	With in normal range
CREATININE	1.59	0.5-0.9 mg/dl	Elevated

The clinical findings of table -2 platelets severely elevated is a marker of thrombocytosis and thyroid disorder and vitamin B12 deficiency increase the risk of likelihood of drug-related processes.

DIAGNOSTIC ASSESSMENT

Patient had an black colored soles and nails with JAK2 V617F positive and had severely high platelets. The relationship of drug administration for thrombocytosis

and having no previous dermatological issue can be strong concern of this reaction.

Naranjo adverse drug reaction probability scale

The Naranjo scale is used to determine the likelihood of the occurrence of ADR. This scale serves as a valuable tool for ADR. By using this scale, a score of 7 is calculated, which is the probable, which is a strong likelihood of the occurrence of an event by the drug.

Table 3: Naranjo scale (adverse drug reaction probability scale).

Naranjo Adverse Drug Reaction Probability Scale				
Question	Yes	No	Do Not Know	Score
1. Are there previous conclusive reports on this reaction?	+1	0	0	0
2. Did the adverse event appear after the suspected drug was administered?	+2	-1	0	+2
3. Did the adverse reaction improve when the drug was discontinued or a specific antagonist was administered?	+1	0	0	0
4. Did the adverse event reappear when the drug was re-administered?	+2	-1	0	+2
Are there alternative causes (other than the drug) that could on their own have caused the reaction?	-1	+2	0	+2
6. Did the reaction reappear when a placebo was given?	-1	+1	0	0
Was the drug detected in blood (or other fluids) in concentrations known to be toxic?	+1	0	0	0
Was the reaction more severe when the dose was increased or less severe when the dose was decreased?	+1	0	0	0
9. Did the patient have a similar reaction to the same or similar drugs in any previous exposure?	+1	0	0	0
10. Was the adverse event confirmed by any objective evidence?	+1	0	0	+1
TOTAL SCORE:				7

Definite: ≥ 9 ; probable: 5-8; possible: 1-4; Doubtful: ≤ 0 .

Final diagnosis

Based on the clinical course, laboratory results and causality assessment, the patient was diagnosed with Hand-foot syndrome induced by hydroxyurea with low hemoglobin level and severe elevated platelets levels-thrombocytosis. The Naranjo Adverse Drug Reaction Probability Scale gave a score of 7, indicating that it was probably related to hydroxyurea.

TREATMENT AND FOLLOWUP

She had been taking the hydroxyurea since 2 month of 500 mg once daily along with her anti-hypertensive medications. She developed the black-colored palms, soles, and nails after continuing to use hydroxyurea medication for two month. She had 1 unit of irradiated PRBC transfusion. Hydroxyurea administration was discontinued. Supportive measures includes application of venusia max hand foot cream and vitamin B12 supplements are followed for the patient.

DISCUSSION

Hydroxyurea is widely used as the first-line cytoreductive treatment for patients with high-risk essential thrombocythemia (ET), especially in elderly individuals and those with the JAK2 V617F mutation. Despite being widely regarded as safe and effective, it can occasionally result in negative skin-related side effects include nail discoloration, hyper-pigmentation, and in rare instances, hand-foot syndrome (HFS).

Edema, erythema, dysesthesia, and hyper-pigmentation of the palms and soles are the hallmarks of HFS. Drug buildup in eccrine sweat glands, direct cytotoxic effects on keratinocytes, and localized inflammatory responses are some of the hypothesized causes.

Within a month of starting hydroxyurea medication, the patient in this instance experienced palmoplantar

hyperpigmentation and nail discoloration. There is evidence for a drug-induced etiology from the time correlation between drug exposure and symptom onset as well as the progression of symptoms over the course of ongoing treatment. A potential relationship is shown by the Naranjo Adverse Drug Reaction Probability Scale score of 7.

CONCLUSION

This case demonstrates how hydroxyurea can occasionally result in hand-foot syndrome, an uncommon but significant skin-related adverse effect that occurs in individuals receiving treatment for high-risk essential thrombocythemia. Clinicians should be mindful of potential cutaneous responses even though hydroxyurea is still the recommended first-line treatment due to its demonstrated efficacy in lowering thrombotic risk. A Naranjo score of seven and the close interval between beginning the medication and the onset of symptoms point to a probable connection between hydroxyurea and the adverse event.

Early detection, judicious clinical assessment, and appropriate adjustment or stopping of therapy are essential to prevent progression and reduce morbidity. This case highlights the value of routine dermatologic monitoring and risk assessment in patients on hydroxyurea therapy, especially in the elderly and those with underlying metabolic or nutritional derangement's.

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